

Literature Review on the Benefits and Harms of social media in Pandemics and Similar Events

Assoc. Prof. Selman Gokce

To cite this article: Selman Gokce, Volume 4, No. 8-5, 2022, p. 148 – 167. - 0099-0001-2209-0106.

Our studies are in a format accredited, approved, and supported by EAALS - European Academic Studies and Laboratory Services. EAALS offers all our works, services, and publications to the world scientists at the stage of carrying our control, accreditation, and support processes to the international platform. ("CURRENT SCIENCE") ("CURRENT SCIENCE") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies -Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

ISSN: 2667-9515

Barcode: 977266795001

Editors Group:

Concessionaire: Tsisana Kharabadze

Dr. Ugur Ugural

Niyaz Bokvadze

Prof. Sabrina Corbi

Prof. Samantha Lewes

Assoc. Prof. Osman Doruk

"" • Current Science Multidisciplinary Academic Journal with Review Panel is a monthly multidisciplinary academic"" ("CURRENT SCIENCE") ("CURRENT SCIENCE") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

journal with a multi-science peer-review." ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

• The magazine is published monthly.

""The magazine will be at the subscriber's address in the first week of the month."" ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("CURRENT SCIENCE") ("CURRENT SCIENCE") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies – Current Science Georgia")

• The journal continues to be included in all international rankings and registrations. Quality articles and publications accelerate this ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") process. ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

"" • Response or rejection time for applications varies between 30 and 90 days."" ("CURRENT SCIENCE") ("CURRENT SCIENCE") ("CURRENT SCIENCE") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

Abstract

Pandemic prevention information is an important tool in the knowledge adoption process, as indicated by the knowledge adoption model (Sussman and Siegal, 2003). This is because anti-pandemic information represents the utility of information. Knowledge about pandemic prevention can be created by GSM's information quality and trust in local government, which may further affect fear among the general public . Wherever the government uses social media to disseminate high-quality information, awareness of COVID-19 preventive activities is raised, contributing to the mitigation of the pandemic. According to the findings of several studies, the use of social media platforms such as Tiktok can facilitate the consumption of public health information and increase both physical and emotional well-being (Basch et al., 2020). In another study, Mensah et al. (2021) discovered that the perceived usefulness of COVID-19 informative e-government services is

positively affected by the quality of information provided by the government. Using various social media platforms (such as microblogs, WeChat, Tiktok , and Twitter), several different are actively working to communicate information about the outbreak and debunk false rumors and disinformation. In conclusion, the hypothesis we think should be considered is Hypothesis 3: A high degree of information quality in GSM has a good effect on anti-pandemic information (H3). According to Sussman and Siegal's (2003) research on ELM, the pathway effect explains how the public's view of the usefulness of information can be directly affected by the credibility of the information source. As a result, confidence in the competence of local government can have a direct impact on the dissemination of information on the control of the pandemic. A study conducted during the Ebola virus epidemic showed that participants with low levels of faith in their government were less likely to take the necessary measures to deal with the epidemic (Blair et al., 2017). This shows that the public's desire to use the information provided by GSM and to take preventive measures increases in direct proportion to the level of trust they have in their government.

Keywords: *social media in Pandemic, Benefits and Harms of social media, Pandemic and social media, social media and Real Information, Unreal Global News in social media*

1. Introduction

A high degree of trust in local government has a good effect on anti-pandemic information (H4). According to ELM , perceived knowledge utility can have an impact on customers' attitudes and opinions (Sussman and Siegal , 2003). For example, Bhattacharjee and Sanford (2006) discovered that if implemented, it would change consumers' perspectives on information technology. Knowing about COVID-19 transmission channels, symptoms and preventive actions during the epidemic is an important part of the value of GSM as an information carrier (Han et al., 2021). It is conceivable that if the general population could grasp such information about pandemic prevention, the levels of anxiety or anxiety caused by the infodemic would decrease. This is because an objective grasp of the epidemic, as well as an effective screening of rumors about it, helps reduce information overload.

Effects of Information Quality on Local Government Trust over GSM This research extends ELM to further explore the effects of the central route on the peripheral route. This study reveals that the quality of information about GSM can increase public trust in the government. Unlike the SARS pandemic that occurred in 2003, the COVID-19 pandemic took place in the age of omnimedia . The dissemination of real-time information on pandemics, government issues, and government-offered opinions and advice are areas where governments can make full use of social media. The public's trust in the local government will be affected by the information that authority publishes via social media.

2. Public Confidence Required for the Effective Implementation of Pandemic Prevention and Control Measures

Previous work also reveals that government plays a constructive role in social media in building the public trust and cooperation necessary for the effective implementation of pandemic prevention and control measures (Larson, 2018; Depoux et al, 2020; Kadam and Atre , 2020). (“Frontiers | The Impact of Government Social Media Information Quality ...”) As a result, depending on the quality of the information disseminated via GSM, the public's trust in the government may increase. Below is a hypothesis we propose:

version of the questionnaire for this research was designed with the help of the above-mentioned keywords and insights from the interview material.

GSM's Quality of Information, Pandemic Prevention Knowledge, Trust in Local Government (which includes second-order variables Talent, Helpfulness, and Integrity) and Public Panic are the four main latent variables measured in this study. Measurement This work also has a public panic component. The measurement elements of these variables are either directly adapted from existing scales or refined using these scales as a starting point. Since different languages are available, each article must be translated in accordance with the translation and back translation processes. This will ensure the reliability and validity of the measurement. Some of the questions were changed after the findings of the focus group interview were analyzed. This was done to

CURRENT SCIENCE

ensure that the structures involved could be reliably evaluated and that residents could understand them. As a result, we identified the six previously mentioned variables with a total of 24 measurement items.

This study refers to the death anxiety scale developed by Belmi and Pfeffer (2016). Social media use is becoming an increasingly important part of our daily lives. Users have exponentially accepted major contemporary social media sites like Facebook since the inception of these platforms, and this adoption continues to expand to this day. Examples of such platforms are Twitter and Instagram. In 2021, around 3 billion people are actively using Facebook every month.

This accounts for more than a third of the world's population. More than forty-five minutes per day of an adult is spent on social media sites. Researching the impact of using social media platforms on the mental health and well-being of users is necessary considering the increasing prevalence and use of these platforms. According to the findings of Brynjolfsson and colleagues [3], digital technologies such as social media platforms provide a significant amount of consumer surplus. To be more specific, they conducted incentive-matched choice experiments to measure the consumer surplus generated by Facebook and found that the average Facebook user in the US earned about \$48 per month from using Facebook in 2017, based on their willingness to accept Facebook. give up access to Facebook for a month. This figure is due to their agreement to give up access to Facebook for one month. Then, they conduct a comparable experiment with students at a leading institution in Europe and discover that the median student in their group earns €97 per month from using Facebook. This finding supports previous hypotheses. While Facebook and other social media services appear to generate significant consumer surpluses and contribute to the economic well-being of their users, there are concerns about negative externalities caused by social media. In addition to academic studies on the impact of social media on an individual's subjective well-being (such as happiness and life satisfaction) and productivity, there is a lively discussion in the media.

The available empirical findings are unclear. There is correlational evidence pointing to a positive, neutral (null results), and negative relationship between social media use and one's well-being. These findings come from a variety of studies (see Haidt for a comprehensive literature review on

CURRENT SCIENCE

social media use and mental health). On the other hand, most of this research has problems with reverse causality and imprecise measures of self-reported use of social media. There is a dearth of definitive causal data on the long-term effects of using social media on one's well-being. Concerns have also arisen in the field of education policy about the impact of students' use of electronic devices, particularly the time they spend on social media, on their academic achievement. Some people find that children's access to social media on their mobile devices makes it harder for them to concentrate on school, which hurts their scores. Because of these concerns, the French ministry of education has decided to restrict the use of mobile phones in all public schools from kindergarten to ninth grade.

In addition, the American Academy of Pediatrics advises parents to limit the time children and adolescents spend on social media so that they have enough time to devote to their academic pursuits. However, a careful examination of the data used in previous correlational research and used as evidence to justify these adjustments reveals that the effects of youth social media use and screen time are not significant enough to warrant changes in policy. Considering widespread concerns about the impact of social media on well-being and conflicting correlational data, timely causal evidence must be collected before any law is enacted in a hurry. We would like to conduct a randomized controlled trial to determine the causal long-term effect of using social media on academic performance and well-being . Our aim is to fill this gap in current studies. Our specific working question is:

Limiting time spent on social media

- a) *general health and happiness,*
- b) *academic success and*
- c) *How does it affect other activities involving the use of digital technology?*

prestigious institution (quarter) in Europe over three academic terms to participate in our research. Participants are instructed to download and install a piece of software called RescueTime on both their personal computers and mobile devices. Throughout the entire research project, this program keeps track of every digital action taken by the participants (subjects). The first term will be used as a benchmark for the remainder of the study. In the second phase of the study, participants are

randomly assigned to a treatment or control group. Members of the treatment group, regardless of the device they use, on social media platforms (Facebook, Instagram, and Snapchat)) limits their time to a maximum of 10 minutes per day. In the third period, we will evaluate the effects after the therapy is completed. We keep an eye on every aspect of our subjects' use of digital technology, including both online and offline actions performed on their various devices, as well as those related to seeking information (such as typing in Microsoft Word or reading a PDF). Our measurements of social media use, like most existing research, are not based on self-reported measures of time spent on social media; instead, our metrics are calculated based on the actual time users spend on social media.

In addition to scores obtained using digital activities, we also collect subjective well-being ratings using surveys, as well as objective performance measures such as grades. Contrary to the findings of previous research based on observational data, our findings do not provide any indication that using social media has a beneficial or adverse effect on a person's well-being (including life satisfaction and mental health). Also, there is no evidence we can find that using social media has any effect on someone's academic performance. However, we see that changing has a big impact. In particular , we see that people in the therapy group reduce the time they spend on social networking platforms and increase the time they spend using instant messaging applications (e.g., WhatsApp) . The total time these people spend on digital devices (computers and mobile phones) can be compared to the time spent by participants in the control group.

3. Exposing social media as the Villain Responsible for Negatively Affecting the Welfare of Society

The first thing we do is explore the common narrative in the media that portrays social media as the villain responsible for negatively impacting society's well-being. This hypothesis is not supported by any evidence we found. Second, both teachers and parents have become more concerned about the impact of digital distractions on children's academic performance, resulting in an increased amount of time children can spend online (for example, through parental control software or getting information from the internet). Our findings suggest that although previous

research has shown the use of electronic devices in the classroom, restricting students' access to social media in any area of their lives (inside or outside the classroom) may not have the intended effect.

Finally, our research is one of the first to yield data suggesting that instant messaging apps and social networking platforms are interchangeable. This has important implications for antitrust regulators, as they assess the market power of major social media platforms like Facebook, which owns Instagram, as well as WhatsApp, a social media service (instant messaging service). The next section of the document is as follows. In the following section, we will present a brief review of current research on the effects of social media use on a person's well-being and academic achievement. In the following paragraphs, we will discuss both the methodology behind our experiment and the data collected during the research. Next, we present the most important findings and then conclude with a discussion of the limitations of this study and some suggestions for where future research should go. Literature on this topic Over the past two decades, many researchers in the fields of psychology, epidemiology, and human-computer interaction (HCI) have become interested in the impact of the Internet in general and social media. he had peace of mind .

Most of this research group is based on self-reported measures of technology use and provides cross-sectional and relational evidence. Kraut and Burke [10] present a review of the relevant literature and express their concerns with cross-sectional or survey-based research due to the presence of several variables that could potentially distort results. Also, correlational studies can be plagued by the large number of investigative degrees of freedom besides the file drawer problem, where only significant results are published. This leads to the impression that relentless use of social media has a positive or negative effect. On the other hand, a null result or trivial conclusions regarding social media use can be a viable conclusion.

4. The Impact of Technology Use on the Person

CURRENT SCIENCE

Orben and Przybylski conduct a specification curve analysis of the data to perform a comprehensive analysis of popular large-scale social datasets ($n = 350k$) used in previous correlational studies investigating the impact of technology use on the person. To this study, all available analytical models are run using a wide variety of covariate configurations. Instead of publishing only some of these analyzes, the results of all of them are published. They discover a modestly negative relationship between the use of digital technology and the psychological health of adolescents. On the other hand, this effect is economically insignificant and does not account for more than 0.4 percent of the change in welfare. In contrast, the authors show that seemingly harmless behaviors such as eating potatoes have the same negative link with excessive technology use. Considering the problems with correlational studies using cross-sectional data, Kraut and Burke advocate using empirical evidence with monitoring data to provide reliable evidence of the link between internet use and one's level. Examining the link between social media use and a person's sense of well-being, the research group revealed a wide variety of results (negative, mixed, positive, and empty). Shakya and Christakis used a longitudinal survey to find a negative relationship between Facebook use and one's well-being.

In contrast, Burke et al. [12] They found a positive correlation between directed communication on Facebook and social well-being. They attribute this finding to the fact that subjects reported increased feelings of social connection and decreased loneliness because of using Facebook. Similarly, Hobbs et al. Paired Facebook profiles with public health records and found that being more socially integrated online (by accepting more Facebook friends) was associated with a reduced risk of death. This was found to be the case when researchers compared individuals who accepted more Facebook friends. According to the findings of Burke and Kraut [14], viewing messages from friends published to all friends and getting one-click feedback was not associated with any improvement in well-being. On the other hand, viewing messages targeted from strong ties was associated with positive improvements in well-being.

For example, increased well-being can lead to increased time spent on social media and vice versa. In the case of digital activities, we found negative correlations between subjective well-being and any digital activity, although these correlations were not statistically significant. Similarly, we find no significant association with social media use. (We'll discuss causality in the next section.) To

explore the possibility of nonlinear effects, we also present correlations with other types of social media use .

However, since the only significant relationships were between life satisfaction measured in survey 1 and social media activity measured after survey, we cannot exclude reverse causality regarding these findings. Communication-related activities, namely instant messaging, and email, show significant positive correlations in the second surveys (for mental health instant messaging and email in terms of life satisfaction) . A consistent, significant negative correlation can be observed for activities in the video category and for life satisfaction (both questionnaires) and mental well-being . This suggests that less satisfied students and those with lower mental well-being at the beginning of the block watched more and more videos in the next block. (“Effects of restricting social media usage on wellbeing and performance ...”)

It has been shown that young people believe that social workers can get help more easily if they use text messaging and Facebook. Moreover, it is an easier way for them to make initial contact and build trust in real life. As a result, we believe that social workers should enter the new internet space more than before. However, this is not a fixed concept. In fact, the cultural understanding of childhood is multifaceted and relative. James and James use the concept of the cultural politics of childhood; This means that childhood is constructed by the interaction of cultural conditions, political mechanisms, and the discourses they create, and operates in ways that both expand and limit children's fields of action. In Nordic countries, social services are uniquely positioned for family policies and are given extensive mandate by law to intervene in cases of child neglect (15). The United States and Northern European countries have taken a similar approach and have recently implemented reforms focused on child protection. While it is difficult to compare different contexts, historical backgrounds, and social welfare systems, we can see this approach becoming an international trend . Protecting children involves professionals understanding new communication patterns. Although social media allows children to share their experiences and feelings, the child's need for care and protection is an important factor in the development of a good psychosocial environment and health. "However, there is also the risk of overestimating the child's competence." (“Child welfare services and social media - Europe PMC”) Understanding the child as an active subject does not eliminate the need for protection and support in a difficult

life situation. Go: Children's best interests – even on the Internet As a result, the child's best interests and needs change over time and context and cannot be defined at once and for all. Society's thoughts about children's and adults' behavior towards children affect how children see themselves and how they interact with others. Although today's welfare state encourages children's participation, children's influence is limited to formal and bureaucratic procedures and language (17,18). In the internet arena, children have more room for action. Therefore, their use of social media forces public services. Children's surfing in social media environments is an example of a change that requires new research into the following questions: What do social workers think about communicating with children through social media? Can social media be used as a tool in case review? "And can the internet enable social workers to reach children in difficult life situations?" ("Child welfare services and social media - CORE") In the last decade, social media has touched the depths of our lives. Many make heavy use of it – the average user spends more than two hours a day on social media connecting and communicating with each other, getting information, and entertaining themselves. "There may be no technology since television that has so dramatically reshaped the way we spend our time." ("Time off social media may leave you less informed but happier") Initially, platforms such as Facebook, Twitter, and Instagram were praised for their potential to facilitate communication and information sharing. Many people today are concerned about potential harm, such as addiction, depression, and political polarization. Although there is much speculation about the potential effects of social media, concrete evidence is relatively scarce. Evidence from a field experiment in a recent article, we present a large-scale randomized assessment of the well-being effects of Facebook, the largest social media platform. We've found that disabling Facebook for a month means people spend more time with friends and family. It also makes them less informed about the news, less polarized in their political views, and a little happier and more satisfied with their lives. We find that users want Facebook back after taking a break from Facebook but use it significantly less than before the "detox". Our findings are in line with other important studies on the same subject.

Study design How did we arrive at these conclusions? We recruited 1,600 US Facebook users online and randomly selected them as a "disable" and a "control" group. The opt-out group received \$102 for staying away from Facebook for the 4 weeks leading up to the US midterm

CURRENT SCIENCE

elections in November 2018; the control group continued to use Facebook as usual. We surveyed both groups twice on their time use, well-being, news information, and political attitudes – once in October, before the start of the opt-out period, and once in November after the opt-out period ended. We then compared the changes in these results in the deactivation group with those in the control group. Detailed findings People in the deactivation group followed our instructions: We verified deactivation by regularly pinging users' Facebook pages and found that 90% of them had not reactivated their accounts within a 4-week period.

Our respondents' responses to the free answer questions and follow-up interviews clarify the various ways Facebook can improve people's lives as a source of entertainment, a means of organizing a charity or activist group, or a vital social lifeline.

Any discussion of the negative aspects of social media should not hide the basic fact that social media fulfills deep and pervasive needs. However, our results also make it clear that the negative aspects are real. We found that four weeks without Facebook improved subjective well-being and significantly reduced post-experiment demand, suggesting that forces like addiction may cause people to use Facebook more than they normally would. We find that disabling makes people less informed, but also less polarizes them, at least by some measures, consistent with concerns that social media is playing a role in the recent rising polarization in the US. The trajectory of opinion on social media – with early optimism about the great benefits sounding the alarm about the potential harm – is a familiar one . Alongside the significant existing work of other researchers, we hope that our analysis can help move the debate from simple cartoons to concrete evidence and offer a plausible assessment of how a new technology affects both individual people and larger social institutions.

Opting out reduced participants' factual knowledge of news and politics, but participants were not less likely to vote or click on email links related to political causes. Polarization can cause citizens to question democratic outcomes; Social media increases polarization because it allows people to choose ideologically appropriate news sources. Deactivation reduced exposure to appropriate news sources. The deactivation reduced polarization on policy issues (such as whether free trade is good or bad) by up to 42 percent.

5. Commercial Television Competition for Both Audience and Advertising Revenue in Many Other Countries

Similarly, PSB and commercial television compete for both viewership and advertising revenue in many other countries, but they still are not always easily distinguishable from a programming point of view. The assumption based on Hotelling's law is that fierce competition between (public and commercial) broadcasters can lead to excessive uniformity. It is not yet clear whether this law applies in practice. However, while the PSB receives government funding, commercial broadcasters are taxed and may even have to pay license fees for use of the radio spectrum. ("Measuring the Welfare Effects of Public Television - tandfonline.com") From an economic perspective, government financing is only effective if it resolves market failures. The question, then, is whether PSB is fixing the market failure or cannibalizing commercial publishers. In most articles, only market failures are assumed to exist (Brown, 1996b; Picard & Siciliani, 2013; Van der Wurff & Van Cuilenburg, 2001) or the concept of market failure is rejected (Tjernström & Tjernström, 2008). Coase (1966) concluded that as early as 1966, the assumption that market failures do indeed persist in publishing requires extensive academic analysis. Anderson and Coate (2005) took the glove and analyzed the conditions under which it was possible to market socially valuable programming using an advertising model. Models of market supply a priori impossible shows that it is not. Armstrong (2005) gives a broader analysis of market failures. He concluded that subscription television had overcome many market failures. For example, publishing is no longer a public good because it can no longer be excluded. Piracy aside, it's possible to exclude people who don't pay for free rides. Armstrong also rationalizes the outside influence argument put forward by many authors (e.g., Meijer, 2005). According to Armstrong, there may be externalities and "citizenship-enhancing" effects. Such effects will be positive when television educates people or makes them more community-oriented, more tolerant, or more informed voters. Also, think of people who talk or tweet about a program that spawned a political, environmental, or medical scandal. On the other hand, Armstrong explained that these externalities are hindered because people's ability to avoid content that is unattractive, but perhaps socially desirable,

CURRENT SCIENCE

increases. Also, externalities can be negative if, for example, watching violence on television causes violent behavior.

However, in accordance with much of the literature, it is assumed here that external effects will be predominantly positive if they occur. Note that this does not automatically mean that government subsidies are justified from an economic perspective. Another issue concerns the shrinking of government budgets. In times of austerity, governments may be forced to rethink their role in broadcasting in line with the discussion of market failures above: What public interests are they protecting by procuring PSB? How is the continued digitization and growth of commercial broadcasting impacting the need for PSB? What market failures justify public broadcasting and do the social and economic benefits outweigh the costs?

6. Far Beyond the Concept of Austerity

The need to ask these questions goes far beyond the concept of austerity. Although public broadcasting in Europe is constrained by state aid regulations³, it is forgivable to wonder what the economic terms of engagement should be when public institutions compete with private providers in a market. This article describes the findings of a case study conducted in the Netherlands. The research explored the pro-social benefits of public service broadcasting (PSB) at both the program level and the collective level. He also compared public television to commercial television. Its history is with seven commercial channels (i.e., RTL4, 5, 7, and 8) offered by RTL Nederland Holdings and SBS Broadcasting (i.e., Net5, SBS6 and Veronica). While there are some distinct differences between the social groups targeted by the different channels, there is a great deal of overlap between these groups and the channels are all public channels. PSB shows had slightly higher ratings: These are NOS and NTR, and their primary responsibilities are to provide programming focused on news, sports, and culture. The programming of the three public channels is overseen by eight PSB associations. These associations receive government funding but operate independently of the government. They also try to serve the private interests of their members in their programs. The number of members of each PSB organization has traditionally been used as a criterion to determine how funds and airtime are distributed among these organizations.

When these associations were founded in the Netherlands, society was very rigidly divided into religious and political groups. This continued until about 90 years ago. Each association was a representative of one of the various groups. Today, the clear lines describing each of these groups are often blurred, and individuals are less likely to join or remain part of one. As a direct result of this, membership is likely to have decreased and the differences between programs are likely to have become less pronounced. After peaking in 1992, when 62% of Dutch households were members of a broadcasting organization, that number has steadily dropped to its current level of 46% in 2014.⁶ Summary: As the policy question and outline fades, this measure increasingly out of date. This fact is recognized by the Dutch Government Policy Science Council and the Cultural Council, both of which serve as key advisers to the Dutch government. The decision not to distribute funds based on the number of members was taken by the Minister of Culture in 2012; instead, the Minister chose to allocate funds based on quality and creativity. Up to this point there has been no new approach to allocation. This gap is filled with this article. This article has addressed the question of whether it is possible to objectively analyze the social impact of programs shown on public television and whether a measure can be devised to achieve this goal.

As a result of this amount being much larger than the current government subsidy per family for the public broadcaster PTS, it was concluded that participants strongly appreciated PSB and its possible benefits for families. They combine disclosed preferences about subscriptions to various channel packages at varying rates with views and sociodemographic data for each channel to assess the payout readiness for each channel and the results of package creation.

7. Conclusion

A family's willingness to pay for access to a particular channel is expected to be proportional to the time members of the household spend watching that channel. To use this approach to measure PSB's impact on social well-being, there must be fluctuations in price and subscription rates for packages containing the various channel arrays PSB offers. Such information is not accessible to the Netherlands or any other country with a free over-the-air PSB. The current work adds to the current research body by exploring a different method that starts with the idea that there are

opportunity costs associated with time. By doing so, it fits into the methodology proposed by Goolsbee and Klenow (2006) for estimating the total welfare of consumers from the leisure time spent online from the opportunity cost of time based on hourly wages . This methodology was developed to calculate the total welfare that consumers derive from the time they spend online as part of their leisure activities. Another advantage of the methodology presented in this study is that it can be applied not only at the level of individual programmes, but also at the level of PSB associations, channels and PSB. It takes advantage of both shown and specified preferences.

8. References

- American Academy of Pediatrics. American Academy of Pediatrics Announces New Recommendations for Childrens Media Use. 2019 [Cited 2019 May 11]. Available from: <https://www.aap.org/en-us/about-the-aap/aap-press-room/Pages/American-Academy-of-Pediatrics-Announces-New-Recommendations-for-Childrens-Media-Use.aspx> .
- Barthes, Roland. 1977. Rhetoric of the Image. In *Image - Music - Text* (translated by Stephen Heath), 32-51. New York: Hill and Wang.
- Mister , Nancy. 2010. *Personal Connections in the Digital Age*. Cambridge: Polity.
- Berger, Jonah, and Katherine Milkman. 2010. *Social Transmission, Emotion, and the Virality of Online Content*. Marketing Science Institute Working Paper Series 2010 Report No. 10-114. Accessed 23 November 2016. <http://marketing.wharton.upenn.edu/documents/research/Virality.pdf> .
- Cheng J, Burke M, Davis EG. Understanding perceptions of problematic Facebook use: When people experience negative life impact and a lack of control. In Proceedings of the 2019 CHI conference on human factors in computing systems 2019 May 2 (pp. 1–13).
- Chisita Collence , T. (2020). Libraries during the coronavirus (COVID-19):

- researchers experience in dealing with the vexatious infodemic . *Library Hi Tech News* 37, 11–14. doi: 10.1108/LHTN-03-2020-0022
- Cyr, D., Head, M., Lim, E., and Stibe , A. (2018). "Using the elaboration likelihood model to examine online persuasion through website design." ("Using the elaboration likelihood model to examine online persuasion ...") *Inf. manag* _ 55, 807–821. doi: 10.1016/j.im.2018.03.009
- DeLone , WH, and McLean, ER om i . s. (2003). The DeLone and McLean model of information systems success: a ten-year update *J. Manag* . ("Cultural orientations and information systems success in public and ...") *Inf. syst.* 19, 9–30. doi: 10.1080/074221222.2003.11045748
- Depoux , A., Martin, S., Karafillakis , E., Preet, R., Wilder-Smith, A., and Larson, H. (2020). The pandemic of social media panic travels faster than the COVID-19 outbreaks . *J Travel Med.* 27:taa031. doi: 10.1093/ jtm /taaaa031
- Dienlin T, Johannes N. The impact of digital technology use on adolescent well-being. *Dialogues in clinical neuroscience.* 2022 Apr 1.
- Dijkstra, TK, and Henseler , J. (2015). Consistent partial least squares path modeling. *MIS Q.* 39, 297–316. doi: 10.25300/MISQ/2015/39.2.02
- Eysenbach , G. (2002). Infodemiology : the epidemiology of (mis) information. *am. J.Med.* 113, 763–765. doi: 10.1016/S0002-9343(02)01473-0
- Eysenbach , G. (2009). Infodemiology and infoveillance : framework for an emerging set of public health informatics methods to analyze search, communication, and publication behavior on the internet. ("Entomology and invigilances: framework for an emerging set of ...") *J.Med. Internet Res.* 11:e11. doi: 10.2196/jmir.1157
- Haidt J. Social Media Use and Mental Health: A Review. 2019 [Cited 2019 May 6]. Available from: <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1w-HOfseF2wF9YIpXwUUtP65-olnkPyWcgF5BiAtBEy0/> .

- Kelly, Maura. 2010. Regulating the Reproduction and Mothering of Poor Women: The Controlling Image of the Welfare Mother in Television News Coverage of Welfare Reform. *Journal of Poverty* 14: 76-96.
- KhosraviNik , Majid and Johann W. Unger. 2015. Critical Discourse Studies and social media : Power, Resistance and Critique in Changing Media Ecologies. (“Critical Discourse Studies and social media: power, resistance and ...”) "In *Methods of Critical Discourse Studies* (3rd ed.), edited by Ruth Wodak and Michael Meyer, 205-233." (“There is a substantial body of literature that - Course Hero”) London: SAGE Publications.
- Kien , Grant. 2013. Media Memes and Prosumerist Ethics: Notes Toward a Theoretical Examination of Memetic Audience Behaviour. (“(PDF) Media Memes and Prosumers Ethics: Notes Toward a Theoretical ...”) *Cultural Studies & Critical Methodologies* 13 (6): 554-561.
- Kim, Young- Chul and Greg C. Loury. 2014. Social Externalities, Overlap and the Poverty Trap. *The Journal of Economic Inequality* 12 (4): 535-554.
- Knezevic , Irena, Heather Hunter, Cynthia Watt, Patricia Williams, and Barbara Anderson. 2014. Food Insecurity and Participation: A Critical Discourse Analysis. (“There is a substantial body of literature that - Course Hero”) *Critical Discourse Studies* 11 (2): 230-245.
- Knobel , Michele and Colin Lankshear , eds. 2007. *Online Memes, Affinities and Cultural Production*. New York: Peter Lang Publishing, Inc.
- Koenig, Thomas. H. and Michael L. Rustad . 2015. Digital Scarlet Letters: Social Media Stigmatization of the Poor and What Can Be Done. (“Indexes to Volume 93 - CORE”) *Nebraska Law Review* 93 (3): 592-635.
- Kraut R, Burke M. Internet use and psychological well-being: Effects of activity and audience. *Communications of the ACM*. 2015 Nov 23;58(12):94–100.

- Kwasnik , Barbara and Kevin Crowston .
2005. Genes of Digital Documents:
Introduction to the Special Issue.
Information, Technology & People
18(2): 76-78.
- Lange, Patricia G. 2009. Videos of Affinity
on YouTube. In *The Youtube Reader*
, edited by Pelle Snickars and Patrick
Vonderau , 228-247. Stockholm:
Wallflower Press.
- Lens, Vicky. 2002. Welfare Reform,
Personal Narratives, and the Media .
Journal of Poverty 6 (2): 1-20.
- Lin, YM, Fu, TT, Yeh, P., & Huang, MY
(2013). "Assessing the economic
value of Public Service Broadcasting
in Taiwan using the contingent
valuation approach." ("Assessing the
Economic Value of Public Service
Broadcasting in Taiwan ...") *Journal
of Media Economics* , 26(4), 186–
202. [[Taylor & Francis Online](#)] ,
- Lister, Ruth. 2004. *Poverty*. Cambridge:
Blackwell/Polity Press.
- MacKinnon, Shauna. 2013. *Decolonizing
Employment: Aboriginal Inclusion in
Canada's Labor Market* . Winnipeg:
University of Manitoba Press.
- "Masur PK. Digital communication effects
on loneliness and life satisfaction."
("Gender Differences in the
Relationships between Meaning in
Life, Mental ...") In *Oxford Research
Encyclopedia of Communication*
2021 Jun 28.
- Meier A, Reinecke L. Computer-mediated
communication, social media, and
mental health: A conceptual and
empirical meta-review.
Communication Research. 2021
Dec;48(8):1182–209.
- O'Hagan, J., & Jennings, M. (2003). Public
broadcasting in Europe: rationale,
license fee and other issues. ("Does
Public Service Broadcasting Serve
the Public? The Future of ...") *Journal
of Cultural Economics* , 27(1), 31–56.
[[Crossref](#)] ,
- Orben A, Dienlin T, Przybylski AK. Social
media's enduring effect on adolescent
life satisfaction. *Proceedings of the
National Academy of Sciences*. 2019
May 21;116(21):10226–8.
pmid:31061122

- Orben A, Przybylski AK. The association between adolescent well-being and digital technology use. *Nature human behaviour* . 2019 Feb;3(2):173–82. pmid:30944443
- Orben A. Teenagers, screens, and social media: a narrative review of reviews and key studies. (“It’s the Content That Counts: Longitudinal Associations between Social ...”) *Social psychiatry and psychiatric epidemiology*. 2020 Apr;55(4):407–14. pmid:31925481
- Pantea , S., & Martens, B. (2014). The value of the Internet for consumers. *IPTS Digital Economy Working Paper 2014/08* . Retrieved from: <http://ssrn.com/abstract=2446962>
- Picard, RG, and P. Siciliani (eds.) (2013). *Is there still a place for Public Service Television? Effects of the changing economics of broadcasting* . University of Oxford: Reuters Institute for the Study of Journalism Report. (“**Reuters Institute Digital News Report 2021 - SSRN**”)
- Rothbauer , J., & Sieg , G. (2013). Public Service Broadcasting of sport, shows, and news to mitigate rational ignorance. *Journal of Media Economics* , 26(1), 21–40. [[Taylor & Francis Online](#)] , ,
- Rubin AJ, Peltier E. France Bans Smartphones in Schools Through 9th Grade. Will It Help Students? *The New York Times*. 2018 September 20 [Cited 2019 May 11]. Available from: <https://www.nytimes.com/2018/09/20/world/europe/france-smartphones-schools.html> .
- Sewall CJ, Goldstein TR, Wright AG, Rosen D. Does Objectively Measured Social-Media or Smartphone Use Predict Depression, Anxiety, or Social Isolation Among Young Adults? *Clinical Psychological Science*. 2022 Mar 25:21677026221078309.
- Solberg, HA (2008). Response: Public Service Broadcasters will survive without expensive sports programs: A response to Tjernström and Tjernström . (“(PDF) Public Service Broadcasters Will Survive Without ... - ResearchGate”) *Journal of Media*

- Economics* , 21(4), 264–269. [[Taylor & Francis Online](#)] , ,
- Solberg, HA (2007). "Commentary: Sports broadcasting: Is it a job for Public Service Broadcasters?" ("COMMENTARY: Sports Broadcasting: Is it a Job for Public Service ...") A welfare economic perspective. *Journal of Media Economics* , 20(4), 289–309. [[Taylor & Francis Online](#)] , ,
- Tjernström , S., & E. Tjernström (2008). Rational foolishness would destroy a Public Service Broadcasting system. *Journal of Media Economics* , 21(4): 258–263 [[Taylor & Francis Online](#)] , ,
- Tweede Kamer. (2011–2012). 33 000 VIII: *Vaststelling van de begrotingsstaten van het Ministerie van Onderwijs , Cultuur most Wetenschap (VIII) voor het jaar 2012* , Nr. ("Kiersten 33000-VIII, nr. 184 | Overheid.nl > Officials bekendmakingen") 59. Brief van de minister van Onderwijs , Cultuur most Wetenschap _
- Van der Wurff , R., & van Cuilenburg , J. (2001). "Impact of moderate and ruinous competition on diversity: The Dutch television market." ("Impact of Moderate and Ruinous Competition on Diversity: The Dutch ...") *Journal of Media Economics* , 14(4), 213–229. [[Taylor & Francis Online](#)] , ,